

ESTIMATION OF BISMUTH. PART VII. GRAVIMETRIC ANALYSIS WITH PHENYLARSONIC ACID

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Further investigations have been carried out on the conditions and limits of precipitation of Bi, separation of Bi from thalious salts and alkaline earths as well as on the composition of the Bi compound.

In Part I of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 119) gravimetric methods for the estimation of bismuth in presence of a large number of ions with the reagent phenylarsonic acid have been described. A tentative formula $C_6H_5AsO_3 \cdot BiOH$ for the bismuth compound of the reagent was suggested. Results of further investigations on the composition of the bismuth compound, the conditions of precipitations and the precipitation limit for bismuth, and the separation of bismuth from alkaline earths and thalious salts have been reported in the present paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Composition of the Bismuth salt of Phenylarsonic Acid.—The precipitate obtained by following either of the procedures I and II described in Part I (*loc. cit.*), after being well washed with hot water, was dried at 110-120° to a constant weight. A weighed amount was decomposed by boiling with caustic soda solution. Arsenic in the filtrate was precipitated and estimated as As_2S_3 . From the residue bismuth was estimated as Bi_2O_3 . (i) 0.2586 g. gave 0.1398 g. Bi_2O_3 , whence Bi=48.49 per cent. (ii) 0.1914 g. gave 0.1037 g. Bi_2O_3 and 0.0686 g. As_2S_3 , hence Bi=48.6; As=17.3 per cent. Further 0.1569 g. of substance on combustion gave 0.1024 g. of CO_2 and 0.0231 g. of H_2O , from which C=17.8; H=1.64 per cent.

Precipitation limit for Bismuth.—Very dilute solutions of bismuth of concentrations ranging from one part of bismuth in 10,000 parts and more of water were examined. To 10 c.c. solution a few drops of the reagent and ammonium acetate were added and gently heated. Distinct precipitates were observed up to 1 part of bismuth in 2,050,000 parts of water. Solutions of greater dilution produced opalescence.

Reagent.—In the following experiments reagents and chemicals used were the same as was used previously (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 119).

Standard solutions.—Bismuth solution was prepared in the same way as in Part I (*loc. cit.*). Solutions of calcium, barium and magnesium nitrates were prepared from their respective carbonates (proanalyse of Kahlbaum) and that of strontium from nitrate (pure quality of Kahlbaum); the strength of the solutions being determined by the usual methods. For thallium, Merck's pure thalious sulphate was used, and thallium in the solution was determined as thalious iodide.

Separation of Bismuth from Alkaline Earth Salts.—The method outlined under Procedure II in Part I (*loc. cit.*) was followed and the results obtained are given below in Table I.

TABLE I

Metals taken.	Reagent added	Weight of bismuth ppt.	Bismuth found	Error	
Bi	0.0391 g.	15 c.c.	0.0796 g.	0.0390 g.	—0.0001 g.
Ca	0.0213				
Ba	0.0355				
Mg	0.0152				
Sr	0.023				
Bi	0.0391	15	0.0794	0.0389	—0.0002
Ca	0.0426				
Ba	0.0710				
Mg	0.0304				
Sr	0.046				

Separation of Bismuth from Thallous Salts.—As the sulphate of thallium was used, the procedure followed was exactly the same as described in Part I (*loc. cit.*) for the estimation of bismuth in presence of sulphate ions. Results appear in Table II.

TABLE II

Metals taken	Reagent added	Wt. of Bi ppt.	Bi found	Error	
Bi	0.0391 g.	15 c.c.	0.0795 g.	0.0390 g.	—0.0001 g.
Tl	0.1223				
Bi	0.0391	15	0.0797	0.0391	Nil
Tl	0.0611				

Critical Studies in the Conditions of Precipitation

A critical study was made to establish the conditions under which bismuth may be completely precipitated and thus may be separated from other elements. The following tables show some of the results of a large number of trial experiments carried out for the purpose.

During the estimation of bismuth in presence of ammonium acetate and acetic acid it was found that the quantity of the reagent required to precipitate bismuth should be at least three times the amount of bismuth present (*cf.* experimental procedure, pp. 121-122 in Part I, *loc. cit.*). The results in Table III show the effect of variation.

TABLE III

No.	Bi taken.	Reagent added.	Total vol.	Weight of bismuth ppt.	Bismuth found	Error
*1	0.0250 g.	5 c.c.	200-250 c.c.	..	..	..
**2	0.0250	5	200-250	..	..	..
**3	0.0250	5	200-250	0.0478 g.	0.0234 g.	—0.0016 g.
**4	0.0250	5	200-250	0.0480	0.0235	—0.0015
5	0.0300	10	200-250	0.0612	0.0300	Nil
6	0.0300	10	200-250	0.0610	0.0299	—0.0001
7	0.0300	10	200-250	0.0610	0.0299	—0.0001
8	0.0250	10	200-250	0.0508	0.0249	—0.0001
9	0.0250	15	200-250	0.0510	0.0250	Nil

*Precipitate gelatinous, very difficult to filter and wash.

**In presence of 20 c.c. ammonium acetate, about 4 to 5 c.c. of acetic acid (2N) were required to make the precipitate crystalline but low results were still obtained.

It was also observed that on the addition of sodium acetate to a bismuth solution containing just enough nitric acid to prevent hydrolysis, the bismuth was completely precipitated with a nearly stoichiometric quantity of the reagent (*cf.* experimental procedure, p. 121 in Part I, *loc. cit.*). The following data were obtained.

TABLE IV

No.	Bi taken.	Reagent added.	Sodium acetate.	Total vol.	Weight of bismuth		Error.
					Bi ppt.	Bi found.	
1	0.0250 g.	10 c.c.	20 c.c.	200-250 c.c.	0.0510 g.	0.0250 g.	Nil
2	0.0250	10	10	200-250	0.0512	0.0251	0.0001 g.
3	0.0300	10	10	200-250	0.0612	0.0300	2%
4	0.0250	5	10	200-250	0.0512	0.0251	0.0001
5	0.0250	5	10	200-250	0.0508	0.0249	-0.0001
*6	0.0250	3	10	200-250	..	..	..
*7	0.0250	3	10	200-250	..	..	..
8	0.0250	3.5	5	200-250	0.0512	0.0251	0.0001
9	0.0250	3.5	5	200-250	0.0510	0.0250	Nil

*Precipitate did not become crystalline.

Further it was found that if the solution contains just sufficient nitric acid (dilute) to keep bismuth in solution, the metal can be completely precipitated by the reagent without the addition of sodium acetate. But the solution should be boiled for about 25 to 30 minutes to make the precipitate crystalline. The precipitate thus obtained requires a long time, preferably overnight, to settle; moreover, under this condition bismuth cannot be separated from a large number of elements. With excess of acid low results were obtained.

TABLE V

No.	Bi taken.	Reagent added.	Total vol.	Weight of bismuth		Error.
				ppt.	found.	
*1	0.0685 g.	20 c.c.	170 c.c.	0.1595 g.	0.0684 g.	-0.0001 g.
*2	0.0250	10	200-250	0.0512	0.0251	0.0001
*3	0.0250	10	200-250	0.0512	0.0251	0.0001
†4	0.0685	15	350	0.1345	0.0660	-0.0025
†5	0.0685	15	350	0.1322	0.0649	-0.0036
‡6	0.0685	15	170	0.1336	0.0655	-0.0030

* The filtrate on testing with H_2S was found to be free from bismuth.

† The solution contained about 3 c.c. of conc. HNO_3 and the filtrate was found to contain bismuth (with H_2S).

‡ The solution contained about 10 c.c. of normal nitric acid and the filtrate was found to contain bismuth (with H_2S).

Bismuth can also be completely precipitated from a solution which was just neutralised with ammonia (using Wesselow's indicator) after the addition of the reagent and acidified with a few drops (4 to 6) of dilute acetic acid (2*N*) as shown below. Also under this condition bismuth cannot be separated from a large number of elements.

TABLE VI

No.	Bi taken.	Reagent added.	Total vol.	Weight of bismuth		Error.
				ppt.	found.	
1	0.0250 g.	3.5 c.c.	200-250 c.c.	0.0510 g.	0.0250 g.	Nil
2	0.0250	3.5	200-250	0.0512	0.0251	0.0001 g.
3	0.0250	3.5	200-250	0.0512	0.0251	0.0001

It may be remarked that the conditions outlined in the experimental procedures given in Part I (*loc. cit.*) for the gravimetric estimation of bismuth are the best that could be obtained, as they are by no means too rigid for an experimenter carrying out a rapid estimation. Other salient features may also be noted :

(i) Boiling for 5 to 7 minutes with stirring is enough to give good crystalline precipitate which settles quickly and can be very easily filtered and washed within 15-20 minutes.

(ii) It enables the separation of bismuth from a large number of elements.

(iii) The complete estimation, involving precipitation, filtration, washing and drying, never requires more than an hour and a half.

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